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IDENTIFICATION AND CLASSIFICATION OF MIGRATION THREATS

Abstract:

The movement of people due to the increased migration pressure determined by the geopolitical situation generates events affecting broadly understood security. Challenges and threats as negative events accompanying the mobility of people focus, among others, on the availability of methods of illegal border crossing and activities centered around the illegal movement of goods and services, generating a priority impact on the security of the state and the migrant. "The most important threats to citizens, society, and consequently also to the state are crimes related to illegal migration, human trafficking, child pornography, as well as all types of smuggling activities (cigarettes, alcohol, fuels, works of art, precious metals) and drugs trafficking".¹

The aim of the study was to present the semantics of the concept of threat from a systemic perspective, including migration threat, as well as to indicate the main migration threats, their sources and risks.

Key words: threat, challenge, migration

Introduction

The movement of individuals and social entities has been a phenomenon accompanying Europe since the beginning of its history. As Klaus Bade writes, "Homo migrans 'has existed just as long as 'Homo sapiens', as moving from place to place is a condition of human existence – similar to births, diseases and deaths".² Their intensity and directions are changing, but the contemporary situation in Europe, although characterized by some unique features related to progressive globalization and the role of non-European political conflicts, is basically nothing special. However, the conditions in Europe chosen as the destination of migration are characteristic.

The undisputed success of the EU is the creation of an area without borders in which freedom of movement applies, conditioning the absence of internal border controls. However, the exercise of

¹ Three global smuggling routes. This is how drugs reach the market, <http://tvn24bis.pl/ze-swiata,75/narkotykowy-biznes-trzy-swiatowe-przemynicze-trasy,555248.html> (07/01/2016).

² K. Bade, *Migration in European History*, Malden-Oxford 2003, s. IX, [after:] M. Praczyk, *Historia migracji w Europie. Próba wykładu*, [in:] *Edukacja migracji. Edukacja międzykulturowa w kontekście kryzysu migracyjnego z perspektywy krajów V4* (ebook), Białystok 2017, p. 27.

freedom of movement implies the need to protect the external and internal borders of the EU/Schengen area.

Migration is a serious challenge to the functioning of the area of free movement. The growing number of immigrants causes tensions and divisions between EU countries due to concerns about the internal security of the Community and member states. Due to its complexity, dispersed nature and numerous internal contradictions, its impact is clearly different from other types of challenges. Migrants who enter the EU/Schengen area in an uncontrolled manner, as an area without internal borders, constitute one of the most serious threats to the stability and security of the European area. Every year, the World Economic Forum publishes a report on the greatest threats to the world in the next decade. WEF interviews approximately one thousand experts (politicians, economists, scientists, activists of social organizations) who point out issues that are particularly problematic for the world. The 2016 diagnosis showed that the migration crisis is the greatest threat. Challenges related to migration evolve, transform into one another and become defined trends that society must prepare for and live with³.

Systemic interpretation of the migration threat

There is no general agreement on the semantics of the concept of threat. In colloquial language, it is understood as a subjectively or objectively dangerous event that may refer to a single entity, a group of entities, an object or a specific system.

The interpretation of the threat category is ambivalent and antinomic. Brunon Hołyst refers to the ambiguity when he states that "the threat is not clear, it is a situation realized by the object that is affected by a given event"⁴.

It may be "a state of the psyche or consciousness caused by the perception of phenomena that are assessed as unfavorable or dangerous. Assessments made by a given entity are particularly important here, as they form the basis of actions taken to strengthen its security. In this approach, the threat is within the sphere of consciousness and is of a subjective nature"⁵. Barbara Bronisławska reduces the

³ See, P. Maciejewicz, *Największe zagrożenie dla świata: kryzys migracyjny*, <http://wyborcza.biz/biznes/1,147584,19478728,najwieksze-zagrozenie-dla-swiata-kryzys-migracyjny.html?disableRedirects=true> (accessed: 20.10.2018).

⁴ B. Hołyst, *Wiktymologia*, Warsaw 1997, pp. 64-65.

⁵ R. Zięba, *Współczesne wyzwania dla bezpieczeństwa międzynarodowego*, „Stosunki Międzynarodowe – International Relations” 2016, No. 3, vol. 52, p. 911.

understanding of threat to a narrow understanding of it as a difficult situation⁶, which we have to deal with when „(...) there is born in the person a fear of losing highly prized values with own life in the first place”⁷.

This may be accompanied by:

- risk of damage occurring,
- dangerous circumstances or events causing damage.

It is the opposite of security, causing anxiety and a sense of lack of certainty and balance⁸. It comes down to creating a dangerous situation experienced by a person functioning in society, his fears for life and the integrity of other values important to him, which may be determined by natural or intentional causes. "A threat means some phenomenon or just a disproportion in resources that causes concern, fear and anxiety"⁹. Due to the above, it can be assumed, to a high degree of generality, that a threat is the possibility of occurrence of phenomena that are assessed or valued negatively¹⁰.

The threat phenomenon can also be analyzed from an approach that eliminates the category of subjective assessment and reduces it to examining objective events that cause a state of danger. In this perspective, a threat is a "real phenomenon that is assessed as unfavorable or dangerous. It may include factors causing a state of uncertainty and fear"¹¹. This is a situation in which there is a likelihood of a dangerous state occurring for the environment¹². This understanding of the concept of threat is related to the occurrence of actual actions of some entities towards others that are unfavorable or dangerous. These activities threaten or eliminate the basic values and interests of an individual entity and the entire community. They are a real, factual and actual threat. The negative impact of events is not based on a subjective assessment of the feeling of danger, but on the real assessment and measurability of undesirable effects. These are "unfavorable and dangerous to the vital interests and basic values of a given entity (individual or collective) actions of other participants of social life"¹³. The dualism in understanding the threat is noticed by Stefan Korycki¹⁴, who assumes that "on the one hand, it is an often subjective feeling resulting from the assessment of occurring phenomena, and on the other - an objective factor causing a state of uncertainty and fear." According to Andrzej Wróbel¹⁵,

⁶ B. Bronisławska, *Współczesne zagrożenia dla bezpieczeństwa publicznego*, „Zeszyty Naukowe WSEI seria Administracja” 2012, 2 (1), pp. 113-128.

⁷ T. Tomaszewski, *Wstęp do psychologii*, Warsaw 1971, p. 127.

⁸ R. Zięba, *Współczesne wyzwania...*, op. cit., p. 9.

⁹ *Bezpieczeństwo międzynarodowe po zimnej wojnie*, R. Zięba (ed.), Warsaw 2008, pp. 25-26.

¹⁰ See., F.X. Kaufmann, *Sicherheit als soziologisches Und sozialpolitisches Problem*, Stuttgart 1970, p. 176.

¹¹ R. Zięba, *Współczesne wyzwania...*, op. cit., p. 10.

¹² B. Zdrodowski (ed.), *Słownik terminów z zakresu bezpieczeństwa narodowego*, Warsaw 2008, pp. 64-65.

¹³ M. Cieślarczyk, *Niektóre psychospołeczne aspekty bezpieczeństwa, wyzwań, szans i zagrożeń*, „Zeszyty Naukowe AON” 1999, No. 2 (35), p. 233.

¹⁴ S. Korycki, *System bezpieczeństwa Polski*, Warsaw 1994, p. 54.

¹⁵ A. Wróbel, *Mózg, czyli świat subiektywny*, „Wiedza i Życie” 1998, No. 3.

the subjectivity of perception is the effect of the functioning of the brain, which provides a filtered image of reality. The basis for the objectivity of perceiving threats is acquired knowledge, experience and the use of appropriate research methods¹⁶.

Threat, which is an antonym of security, is often included in a too broad set of negatively assessed phenomena. "Some of these phenomena are not so much threats as challenges for entities, i.e. new situations in which indispensable needs arise that require formulating answers and taking appropriate actions. Unresolved challenges may only turn into threats to the security of individuals, societies, nations and states"¹⁷. The consequence of perceiving challenges as difficult situations is the incorrect assessment of them as dangerous events. When analyzing the phenomenon of threats as an antonym of security, it is important to distinguish them from similarly perceived phenomena, such as challenges. This is difficult because both types of events are valued negatively. "The boundary between uncertainty (created by challenges) and threats is fluid, as it depends on the definition of the values that are protected, as well as on the individual sensitivity of the perceiving entity. That is why politicians and some researchers use the term "challenges" to describe both types of phenomena"¹⁸. Challenges, according to Wiesław Śmiałek, are often the so-called new situations that require defining responses and taking appropriate actions. Only unresolved challenges can turn into threats to the security of individuals, nations and states¹⁹. "To simplify, it can be assumed that challenges and threats fall along a certain continuum, which gradually creates a need and then transforms into the need for entities to take action to ensure their security"²⁰.

Due to the multitude of positions on the distinction between threats and challenges, it is reasonable to approach them jointly, treating them as types of risk for national and international security²¹. Taking into account the subject of considerations, the analysis will cover activities aimed at analyzing threats as a real and certain phenomenon that occurs in a specific system of things, i.e. a system. Therefore, it should be assumed that this concept includes events provoked by an intentional factor that have a negative or unfavorable impact on the efficiency of the system by generating a state of uncertainty or danger²².

Migration as a source of threats

¹⁶ B. Wiśniewski, D. Podleś, J. Prońko, *Zagrożenia bezpieczeństwa publicznego*, [in:] *Bezpieczeństwo wewnętrzne RP w ujęciu systemowym i zadań administracji publicznej*, (ed.) B. Wiśniewski, S. Zalewski Bielsko Biała 2006, p. 46.

¹⁷ R. Zięba, *Współczesne wyzwania...*, op. cit., p. 11.

¹⁸ Ibidem; See, V.-I. Ghebali, B. Sauerwein, *European Security in the 1990s: Challenges and Perspectives*, New York – Geneva 1995.

¹⁹ W. Śmiałek, *Ewolucja wyzwań, zagrożeń w doktrynie obronnej i strategii bezpieczeństwa narodowego RP (1990-2015)*, [in:] *Współczesne wyzwania bezpieczeństwa Polski*, (ed.) B. Jagusiak, Warsaw 2015, p. 312.

²⁰ R. Zięba, *Współczesne wyzwania...*, op. cit., p. 12.

²¹ W. Śmiałek, *Ewolucja wyzwań, zagrożeń...*, op. cit., p. 314; R. Zięba, *Współczesne wyzwania...*, op. cit., p. 12.

²² K. Nicoń, *Inżynieria zarządzania kryzysowego. Podejście systemowe*, Warsaw 2007, p. 76.

International migrations, especially mass mobility, are nowadays analyzed in terms of threats to public security and order. "Migration is not a problem, but a social phenomenon that – like many other phenomena – can cause both positive and negative effects. However, in the analysis of actual or even potential (but real) threats, it is worth rejecting this generalization and assuming that it is not migration itself, but its uncontrolled, undesirable manifestations and effects that may become a threat"²³.

When considering the category of migration as a source of benefits and threats, it should be assumed that many factors determine the consequences of people's mobility. To resolve this issue, the political, social and demographic context in which the mobility process takes place are important. The perspective of assessing the phenomenon, conditions and consequences of the process, which can be considered from the perspective of sending, receiving and transit countries, is also far-reaching. An institution involved in migration management and control, i.e. one that guards public order and security, may have a different point of view, as may individuals and their families. Entities active in the migration process also have interests that are often not coherent, i.e. what may be an undesirable phenomenon for the managing institution may be perceived as a measurable benefit for an individual migrant. The implications of mobility will also vary depending on the perspective from which they are considered. Other effects of migration will be identified by economists, sociologists and demographers²⁴.

The migration process is complex and multidimensional, and the threats it determines are multiple and difficult to define. "These threats are multi-aspect in nature, i.e. legal, social, economic and political. Each threat may occur as an independent entity or be a compilation of many circumstances contributing to the feeling of insecurity"²⁵. The issue of migration threats covers a number of events and activities that occur in connection with the process of movement, i.e. crossing the border as well as the fact of settling and creating an environment of life activity in a given place.

Migrations, during which citizens of one country move to another where their life activity is concentrated, pose a challenge to the concepts of state affiliation, nationality and citizenship, as well as the obligations of citizens towards the state. Migration processes not only cause institutional and systemic changes, but also influence the transformation of the social structure of the receiving countries. The influx of migrants is a challenge not only for the state and its institutions, but above all for the host society. Migration may generate threats to social cohesion and stability given the

²³ M. Szulecka, *Migracje jako źródło wybranych zagrożeń porządku prawnego i publicznego. Wnioski z badań jakościowych*, [in:] *Przestępczość cudzoziemców. Aspekty prawne, kryminologiczne, praktyczne*, W. Klaus K. Laskowska, I. Rzeplińska (ed.), Warsaw 2017, p. 427.

²⁴ See, *Ibidem*, p. 427-431.

²⁵ K. . Tomaszycycki, *Procesy migracji – realne czy wirtualne zagrożenie?*, [in:] *Prawne i społeczne aspekty cyberbezpieczeństwa*, S. Gwoździwicz, K. Tomaszewski (ed.), Warsaw 2017, p. 198.

economic burden that migrants may pose. Citizens' awareness that migrants use social benefits and health, social and housing infrastructure may cause resentment and hostility²⁶. "When it comes to challenges for the receiving society, the increase in uncertainty of individuals, the sense of threat and misunderstanding are worth mentioning"²⁷. The influx of migrants is associated with tensions in social relations, strongly linked to identity. Taking into account the functioning of mono-ethnic societies, the increase in the number of migrants and functioning in the realities of cultural pluralism may determine xenophobic or racist behavior.

Assuming that migration is not a negative category, but, like any social phenomenon, generates unfavorable events, the threats resulting from population mobility will be analyzed. From the point of view of the subject of considerations, the area of interest are those groups of negative events that are identified directly with borders and are the area of interest of services managing migration processes and services ensuring public safety and order. The indicated threats have been classified and arranged by Monika Szulecka into three groups, which include:

- threats constituting the so-called migration-related crimes, directly related to crossing the border and legalizing or not legalizing the stay and work of foreigners,
- threats resulting from the way in which state borders are crossed, i.e. threats related to human trafficking, forced labor and other abuses against foreign workers,
- threats related to other types of crimes, including common and economic ones²⁸.

In this context migration threats within the jurisdiction of the Border Guard can be mentioned, i.e.:

- illegal transit and residence migration,
- forging documents entitling a person to cross the border,
- smuggling of goods subject to excise tax, drugs, weapon, ammunition and other goods.

This understanding of the threat is associated with a theoretical approach to a complex of phenomena that can be described as a set of connections between migration and the state of security. On the one hand, the types of border security threats presented above are constantly evolving, but on the other hand, they are directly or indirectly related to each other.

When adopting the indicated classification, it should be noted that the selection of the described threats results from the fact that the above-mentioned negative phenomena appeared in quantitative and qualitative studies of border management services at the level of the European Union and member states. This indicates the deterministic nature of the challenges both for the security of the integration group and for individual countries. Therefore, the reference point are the threats related to the

²⁶ S. Bali, *Ruchy ludności*, [in:] *Studia bezpieczeństwa*, P. D. Williams (ed.), Cracow 2012, p. 481.

²⁷ *Niekontrolowane migracje do Unii Europejskiej*, P. Sasnal (ed.), Warsaw 2015, p. 58.

²⁸ M. Szulecka, *Migracje jako źródło wybranych zagrożeń* ..., op. cit., pp. 430-431.

protection of these borders and the universal measures defined in the Common Integrated Risk Analysis 2.0 methodology²⁹ (CIRAM 2.0).

The term "illegal immigration" in a broad sense is used to describe various phenomena accompanying mobility processes. Participants in the phenomenon of illegal migration are foreigners who illegally enter the territory of the country by land, sea and air. This is often performed through organized crime networks of smugglers and human traffickers and using false or forged documents. The essence of illegal migration, from the formal and legal point of view, is the stay of foreigners contrary to the legal norms in force in a given country, regulating their entry and exit³⁰.

Illegal migration is one of the most serious threats related to population mobility. It is currently perceived as the most dangerous part of migration flows. "The uncountability of the phenomenon of illegal migration is the biggest problem that arises when attempting to analyze it. It results primarily from the illegal nature of the phenomenon, which is the reason for the inability to apply the adopted research methods"³¹. It is a continuous phenomenon that undergoes varying degrees of intensity depending on the political and economic situation in the world. Growing disproportions in the wealth of international society and continuing conflicts lead to migration movements towards Europe continuing. Illegal migration is currently a significant problem for the European Union. This phenomenon affects the economic situation of the community and its internal security. The analysis indicates that it is becoming an organized criminal activity, therefore counteracting it is of priority importance for the countries concerned³². Monitoring migration processes and the threats they generate, as well as fighting illegal migration are a priority resulting from the need to ensure the security of EU borders.

Entering or remaining in the territory of a given country is often done using false or forged documents and through organized crime networks of smugglers and illegal traffickers³³.

Violations of the law related to the use of false documents vary depending on the immigrant's country of origin or possibility of exercising legal mobility. They constitute one of the most important challenges, analyzing migration threats and counteracting them. Using false documents generates fear about one's intentions related to their stay. There is often a presumption that the intention is different

²⁹ The Common Integrated Risk Analysis - CIRAM methodology was created by the Frontex Agency to examine the level of cross-border crime threat. It involves an integrated (based on the same defined measures) examination of the compliance, sensitivity and impact of individual member states to threats such as illegal border crossings, illegal residence, human trafficking, other cross-border crime.]

³⁰ P. Lubiewski, *Nielegalna imigracja. Zagrożenia bezpieczeństwa*, Szczytno 2016, p. 44.

³¹ P. Lubiewski, *Nielegalna imigracja...*, op. cit., pp. 86.-25

³² R. Lewandowski, *Dokumenty a nielegalna migracja i bezpieczeństwo publiczne*, „Warmińsko - Mazurski Kwartalnik Naukowy. Nauki Społeczne” 2015, No. 36, p. 15.

³³ A. Wawrzusiszyn, *Wybrane problemy transgranicznego bezpieczeństwa Polski*, Warsaw 2012, p. 131.

than the declared one. Mobility, like falsifying documents, in such cases is an action aimed at committing a crime and not a process that results in a change of place of life activity.

The threats resulting from migration movements also include smuggling activities. "Smuggling, as illegal transportation across the border, can also be referred to as carrying (...) something illegal"³⁴. Smuggling crimes are largely related to organized crime, the source of which is believed to be in migration processes³⁵.

Smuggling crime, as one of the categories of the most frequently committed crimes, conventionally referred to as border, is also involved in many factors in its causes, and its development is primarily economic. It has a highly negative impact on economic security and the security of the state in general. "The most important threats to citizens, society, and consequently also to the state are crimes related to illegal migration, human trafficking, child pornography, as well as all types of smuggling activities (cigarettes, alcohol, fuels, works of art, precious metals) and drugs trafficking"³⁶.

Summary

Ensuring the security of the European Union's external borders, especially in times of intense migration flows, is a key element of guaranteeing order and balance throughout the territory of the European Union. Migration processes taking place in Europe imply a number of risks and threats. Monitoring them by national and European border services allows us to create a catalog, which includes primarily: illegal border crossing, forging documents and smuggling. Cross-border crimes against the security of the European Union are organized and committed by criminal groups. For this reason, the key element to ensuring an adequate level of protection of external borders and the security of the entire European Union is international cooperation and mutual cooperation of services. Cooperation between European Union Member States, customs and border services of individual countries serves to reduce the level of threats to border security.

Exploring selected aspects of threats to the security of the internal borders of the European Union that negatively affect the security of these areas shows the scale and needs for preventive and follow-up actions.

Experts point out one more aspect: "(...) the protection of the external borders of countries such as Lithuania, Latvia and Estonia is highly unsatisfactory and this is the reason for what is happening on the internal borders (...) At some point, those countries that separated away from this old system [former republics of the USSR] and which are independent states, do not properly fulfill their

³⁴ A. Wawrzusiszyn, *Wybrane problemy...*, op. cit., p. 146.

³⁵ M. Wódka, *Międzynarodowa przestępczość zorganizowana – typologia charakterystyka, zwalczanie*, „De SECURITATE ET Defensione. O Bezpieczeństwie i Obronności” 2015, No. 2(1), p. 156.

³⁶ *Trzy światowe trasy przemytnicze. Tak narkotyki trafiają na rynek*, <http://tvn24bis.pl/ze-swiata,75/narkotykowy-biznes-trzy-swiatowe-przemytnicze-trasy,555248.html> (07.01.2016).

obligations (...) That is why there is a greater threat at the moment on our internal border than on the external one (...) it is a bit ridiculous. It's ridiculous, because the whole of Europe, or even more, thinks that the danger lies on the external border³⁷.

The scale of illegal border crossing is only an estimate as the assessment is based on events disclosed by border protection services. In reality, the scale of illegal border crossings is seriously underestimated. "The lack of ongoing control at border crossings makes it difficult to detect border crime, which in turn translates into a decrease in detected crime, and does not necessarily reflect a decrease in actual crime"³⁸.

Poland is a transit country between eastern and western Europe, especially for illegal migration, but also for smuggling. In this section, most of the suspects identified were citizens of third countries neighboring Poland, i.e. Ukraine and Russia. The numbers of suspected citizens of Ukraine, Russia, Belarus, as well as Georgia, China and Vietnam registered at the internal border prove that Poland is has a transit character in border crime.

Due to the tightening of migration policy in the territory of Western European countries, an increase in the risk of illegal border crossing towards Poland is expected, due to the legalization of stay in the territory of the Republic of Poland and the return to their countries of origin of foreigners who are afraid of being banished from Germany. Issuing a large number of refusals of entry to foreigners at the Polish external border may result in the creation of alternative migration routes. However, the development of the situation in Turkey and Greece may result in the activation of the Balkan route and the use of alternative routes leading through Romania, Hungary, Slovakia and the Czech Republic through Poland to Germany³⁹. "Citizens of other countries reach Poland through many countries, but they often say that the first really safe country is Poland. Therefore, crossing the Polish border is a very important stage of the journey for both smugglers of goods and participants and organizers of the transfer of people⁴⁰.

³⁷ M. Szulecka, *Przejawy nielegalnej migracji ...*, op. cit., p. 219.

³⁸ M. Perkowska, *Dynamika i struktura przestępczości...*, op. cit., p. 178.

³⁹ Analiza zagrożeń na granicy polsko-niemieckiej, 2. Half-year 2018, internal document of the Nadodrzański Border Guard Unit.

⁴⁰ K. Laskowska, *Granica państwa, jako miejsce popełniania przestępstw...*, op. cit., p. 292.

Bibliography

Literature

1. Analiza zagrożeń na granicy polsko-niemieckiej, 2, half-year 2018, internal document of the Nadodrzański Border Guard Unit.
2. Bali S., *Ruchy ludności*, [in:] *Studia bezpieczeństwa*, P. D. Williams (ed.), Cracow 2012.
3. Blade K., *Migration in European History*, Malden-Oxford 2003, s. IX, [after:] M. Praczyk, *Historia migracji w Europie. Próba wykładu*, [in:] *Edukacja migracji. Edukacja międzykulturowa w kontekście kryzysu migracyjnego z perspektywy krajów V4* (ebook), Białystok 2017.
4. Bronisławska B., *Współczesne zagrożenia dla bezpieczeństwa publicznego*, „Zeszyty Naukowe WSEI seria Administracja” 2012, 2 (1).
5. *Bezpieczeństwo międzynarodowe po zimnej wojnie*, R. Zięba (ed.), Warsaw 2008.
6. Cieślarczyk M., *Niektóre psychospołeczne aspekty bezpieczeństwa, wyzwań, szans i zagrożeń*, „Zeszyty Naukowe AON” 1999, No. 2 (35).
7. Ghebali V. I., Sauerwein B., *European Security in the 1990s: Challenges and Perspectives*, New York - Geneva 1995.
8. Hołyst B., *Wiktymologia*, Warsaw 1997.
9. Kaufmann F.X., *Sicherheit als soziologisches Und sozialpolitisches Problem*, Stuttgart 1970.
10. Korycki S., *System bezpieczeństwa Polski*, Warsaw 1994.
11. Laskowska K., *Granica państwa, jako miejsce popełnienia przestępstw przez zorganizowane grupy przestępcze z udziałem cudzoziemców*, [in:] *Przestępczość cudzoziemców. Aspekty prawne, kryminologiczne i praktyczne*, Klaus W., Laskowska K., Rzeplińska I., Warsaw 2017.
12. Lubiewski P., *Nielegalna imigracja. Zagrożenia bezpieczeństwa*, Szczytno 2016.
13. Lewandowski R., *Dokumenty a nielegalna migracja i bezpieczeństwo publiczne*, „Warmińsko - Mazurski Kwartalnik Naukowy. Nauki Społeczne” 2015, No. 36.
14. Nicoń .K., *Inżynieria zarządzania kryzysowego. Podejście systemowe*, Warsaw 2007.
15. *Niekontrolowane migracje do Unii Europejskiej*, P. Sasnal (ed.), Warsaw 2015.
16. Szulecka M., *Migracje jako źródło wybranych zagrożeń porządku prawnego i publicznego. Wnioski z badań jakościowych*, [in:] *Przestępczość cudzoziemców. Aspekty prawne, kryminologiczne, praktyczne*, W. Klaus K. Laskowska, I. Rzeplińska (ed.), Warsaw 2017.
17. Perkowska M., *Dynamika i struktura przestępczości granicznej cudzoziemców w Polsce na podstawie danych statystycznych Służby Celnej (Ministerstwa Finansów)*, [in:] *Przestępczość cudzoziemców. Aspekty prawne , kryminologiczne i praktyczne*, (ed.) Klaus W., Laskowska K., Rzeplińska I., Warsaw 2017.

18. Śmiałek W., *Ewolucja wyzwań, zagrożeń w doktrynie obronnej i strategii bezpieczeństwa narodowego RP (1990-2015)*, [in:] *Współczesne wyzwania bezpieczeństwa Polski*, (ed.) B. Jagusiak, Warsaw 2015.
19. Tomaszewski T., *Wstęp do psychologii*, Warsaw 1971.
20. Tomaszycycki K., *Procesy migracji – realne czy wirtualne zagrożenie?*, [in:] *Prawne i społeczne aspekty cyberbezpieczeństwa*, S. Gwoździwicz, K. Tomaszewski (ed.), Warsaw 2017.
21. Wawrzusiszyn A., *Wybrane problemy transgranicznego bezpieczeństwa Polski*, Warsaw 2012.
22. Wróbel A., *Mózg, czyli świat subiektywny*, „Wiedza i Życie” 1998, No. 3.
23. Wiśniewski B., Podleś D., J. Prońko, *Zagrożenia bezpieczeństwa publicznego*, [in:] *Bezpieczeństwo wewnętrzne RP w ujęciu systemowym i zadań administracji publicznej*, (ed.) B. Wiśniewski, S Zalewski, Bielsko Biała 2006.
24. Wódka M., *Międzynarodowa przestępczość zorganizowana – typologia, charakterystyka, zwalczanie*, „De SECURITATE ET Defensione. O Bezpieczeństwie i Obronności” 2015, No. 2(1).
25. Zięba R., *Współczesne wyzwania dla bezpieczeństwa międzynarodowego*, „Stosunki Międzynarodowe – International Relations” 2016, No. 3, vol. 52.
26. Zdrodowski B. (ed.), *Słownik terminów z zakresu bezpieczeństwa narodowego*, Warsaw 2008.

Internet sources

1. Maciejewicz P., *Największe zagrożenie dla świata: kryzys migracyjny*, <http://wyborcza.biz/biznes/1,147584,19478728,najwieksze-zagrozenie-dla-swiata-kryzys-migracyjny.html?disableRedirects=true>.
2. *Trzy światowe trasy przemytnicze. Tak narkotyki trafiają na rynek*, <http://tvn24bis.pl/ze-swiata,75/narkotykowy-biznes-trzy-swiatowe-przemytnicze-trasy,555248.html>.